

Available Nitrogen in Tropical Soils. Part I.

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Regarding the amounts of available nitrogen (sum of ammoniacal and nitric nitrogen) present in English soils, Russell, ("Soil Conditions and Plant Growth," 1932, pp. 237, 475) has stated as follows:—

"In normal conditions, the nitrate and ammonia together rarely account for more than one per cent. of the nitrogen in the soil."

"Usually the total amount of nitrogen is so large in comparison with the amount of nitrate that the changes in amount fall within the limits of experimental error."

"Neither ammonia nor nitrate normally occurs in the soil in any great quantity; a usual range on land carrying vegetation is from 5 to 25 parts of nitric nitrogen and about 5 to 10 parts of ammonia per million of soil, corresponding to about one to three per cent. of the total nitrogen."

The amount of available nitrogen in Russian soils varies from 0.36 to 4.6%.

In foregoing publications (*cf.* Dhar, "Influence of Light on Some Biochemical Processes," 1935), it has been emphasised that the oxidation processes taking place in the soil are facilitated to a greater extent in tropical countries due to sunlight and higher soil temperatures than in temperate climates. It is expected, therefore, that the percentage of available nitrogen in the tropical soil is greater than in cold countries.

In order to test this point, we have determined the total, ammoniacal and nitric nitrogen of samples of soils collected from different parts of India. Our results can be summarised as follows:—

Assam (Nyagora tea estate). Four samples of soil analysed; the available nitrogen varies from 25.1 to 40.4% of the total nitrogen, of which the variation is from 0.092 to 0.139% of the soil.

Bengal (Dacca and Nadia). Six samples analysed; the available nitrogen varies from 14.3 to 29.7% of the total nitrogen, of which the variation is from 0.057 to 0.227% of the soil.

Bihar (Pusa). Five samples collected in July 1932 and analysed in April 1935; the available nitrogen varies from 28.1 to 47.7% of the total nitrogen, of which the variation is from 0.0238 to 0.0313% of the soil.

United Provinces (Allahabad). (a) Thirteen samples of ordinary

garden soil analysed ; the available nitrogen varies from 10 to 31·6% of the total nitrogen, of which the variation is from 0·0347 to 0·0582% of the soil.

(b) Five samples of molassed soil of which the C: N ratio is constant, analysed ; the available nitrogen varies from 11·7 to 28% of the total nitrogen, of which the variation is from 0·0437 to 0·09% of the soil.

The Punjab.—(Ranjitkot, Hiyatpur and Chhanwali). Three samples analysed ; the available nitrogen varies from 13·4 to 15·2% of the total nitrogen, of which the variation is from 0·04 to 0·0582 % of the soil.

Madras (Waltair). Two samples analysed ; the available nitrogen varies from 15 to 24·9% of the total nitrogen, of which the variation is 0·0309 to 0·0625% of the soil.

The foregoing results show that the amounts of available nitrogen varies from 10 to 47·7% of the total nitrogen in the soils collected from different parts of India. The percentage of available nitrogen of a soil from Bangalore, which is a cool place is 8·5. Hence the portion of available nitrogen in comparison with the total nitrogen in tropical soils is much greater than that present in soils of temperate climates. It appears, therefore, that the solar radiations, which fall on the tropical soil, help in the oxidation of the nitrogenous substances present in the soil, which is rendered suitable for plant growth, although the total nitrogen in tropical soils is generally less than in those of temperate countries.

SUMMARY.

1. Experiments show that the available nitrogen in soils collected from Assam, Bengal, Bihar, United Provinces, the Punjab, and Madras, varies from 10 to 47·7% of the total nitrogen. In English soils, this value is 1% and in Russian soils, it is 0·36 to 4·6%. Hence the available nitrogen in tropical soils is greater than in the soils of temperate climates.

2. It seems that the solar radiations falling on the tropical soil help in the oxidation of the nitrogenous compounds to ammonia and nitrate, which are available for the plants, although the total nitrogen is less in tropical soils than in those of cold countries.